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Research Article

**AN ASSESSMENT OF POTENTIAL PENETRATING HEART
DISEASES AND LUNG DISEASES AMONG PATIENTS
DIAGNOSED WITH BOTH DISEASES**Sara Ijaz, Sohaira Shahid, Hina Tahir
UHS, Lahore**Abstract**

Objective: Multiple research and real-life experiences have alarmingly made the case that heart injury (penetrating) usually carries the fatal potential. It mostly happens because of cardiac blockage or haemorrhage (exsanguinous). Therefore, this research aims to assess the patients who are suffering from lungs and penetrating heart diseases. Furthermore, through this study, we also took an account of findings and results of both ailments as a whole.

Methodology: We included (20) patients who enrolled with lungs and penetrating heart injuries in the hospital and underwent the operation at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore (September 2016 to June 2017). Reports of collective exploration of penetrating heart and lungs damages are based on surgical discoveries by the professionals. In the process of surgeries, specialists mainly displayed their concerns to get rid of cardiac blockage and control over the blood losses. The surgical procedures mainly included the relief of cardiac tamponade, control of bleeding, restoration pulmonary and cardiac lacerations as well as splicing of arteries' bypass according to the requirements.

Results: We examined twenty patients as eighteen were male participants and only two were females. Their age limited between (14 – 60) years and the mean age was (34.8 ± 13.5) years. Seventeen patients reported with stab wounds while resting of three with gunshot injuries. We recorded twenty-two cardiac chambers wound among the sample of twenty patients. The highly reported injury was right ventricle leading to the left ventricle in cardiac chambers. Additionally, two patients also came up with injuries in coronary arteries. The left upper lobe was the most affected lobe in terms of lungs injuries.

Conclusion: We can make the case, on the bases of the findings of this study, that instant reporting to the specialists about the said problems for surgeries can provide more chances of survival. Moreover, we also observed that such heart wounds can also be leading to the accessing chest injuries.

Keywords: CPB, Cardiac Injury and Penetrating.

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INTRODUCTION:

In terms of pulmonary, heart injuries and CABG (coronary artery bypass grafting) we repaired the chambers' injuries with the help of mattress sutures of (3 – 0) polypropylene joined on Teflon or the pledges around the heart. In the cases of larger injuries, we put the first mattress suture in the centre of the wound. To control the atrial injuries, we placed a finger in the affected area. We did the next repair with (5 – 0) polypropylene mattress suture that we situated in a compressed string way. Moreover, for the huge atrial injuries, we used to situate a Satinsky clamp to control it. We applied horizontal mattress suture to mend the coronary artery injuries. We flexibly made a stricture for pericardium by maintaining the space from (1.5 cm – 2 cm). In this way, we actually left some space to pleural cavity and the pericardial window for the drainage. This was a technique to avoid the blockage of blood before surgery. We took the patients to the cardiac ICU before the surgeries. All those cardiac patients observed two-dimensional echocardiography prior to their discharge from retentions in the hospital. Moreover, we file a follow-up session for two months in their postoperative tenure.

These accessing heart injuries may cause the death among the affected because of acute blockage of blood or haemorrhage [1, 2]. Moreover, injuries to the lungs can also add up lethal effects to heart wounds. Therefore, instant surgeries through standard operating procedures can only bring back the patients to life [3]. Many people have attempted to describe the diseases related to heart as Homer, a Greek Poet and Philosopher attempted to explain for the first time through his poetry. He particularly mentioned it through the death of Sarpedon in his poem Iliad [4]. Edwin Smith Papyrus also talked about the penetration of chest injuries like heart malfunctioning [5]. But for the first time, Cappelen attempted to take the medical remedies for the heartaches in 1896. He mended a wound of the left ventricle and medically joined the LAD artery. Unfortunately, the patient did not survive after the surgery. Rehn was the first person who succeeded to mend the wound of the right chamber in the same year that paved the ways of cardiac surgeries [3, 4]. In 1902, Hill got success in the mending of left chamber. With the collection of multiple new cases along with his own experiences, Pool (1912) laid a complete compendium of procedures about cardiac surgical treatments by laying the stress on surgical choice. Many research professionals have shared their part in the administration and management of surgical procedures which are no doubt very helpful. But still, there are some unaddressed challenges which require

immediate consideration [6]. So, this study is designed to file all such cases who reported in our hospital and further received the recommendations for cardiac surgeries. Moreover, this research also made the efforts to document the combined cases of lungs and heart wounds.

METHODOLOGY:

We included (20) patients who enrolled with lungs and penetrating heart injuries in the hospital and underwent the operation at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore (September 2016 to June 2017). Originally, the vicinity hospitals referred these patients with deduced heart injuries on the bases of victims' present situations. Moreover, we carefully diagnosed the existence of lungs and cardiac wound as a collective disruptive troublesome. Because most of the patients reported in emergency departments for with the recommendations of surgeries, therefore, we did not delay to go through the time taking laboratory tests. The patients who reported with stable and controlled blood flow, we took them for echocardiography, electrocardiography, and for the radiography of their chest. We did not operate sub-xiphoid window and pericardiocentesis.

We used thoracotomy or median sternotomy for the detection. In some cases, we applied both the cases. In the surgeries, we originally focused for the release from heart blockage, to the control over bleeding, restoration of

RESULTS:

We evaluated the cases of total numbers of twenty patients; eighteen were males and two were females with the age limit (14 – 60) and the mean age was (34.8 ± 13.5) years. Among these subjects (17) had stab wounds, whereas the other three reported for surgery due to a gunshot. We filed the injuries on the right hemithorax in (14) patients, (3) with bilateral appearance and (3) with the left side. In addition to these cases had wounds in the upper abdominal surface. Lab reports portrayed less than (70mmHg) systolic blood pressure. We took the patients for electrocardiogram who were Hemodynamically unstable. But we obtained additional tests of those patients who were relatively stable. Surgeons sealed pericardial scars with fat and through clotting. And those who started bleeding also underwent through the process of formation of a clot. Specialists applied median sternotomy on (6), left anterolateral thoracotomy on (10) and right on (1), whereas, (2) patients received both left thoracotomy and median sternotomy. The last received both right and left thoracotomies. Two patients required laparotomy because of wounds in liver and spleen, and one as

alternatively received splenectomy. We noted (0.4 cm – 4 cm) length of cardiac injuries with average (2.1). The patients who had diaphragmatic injuries received a non-absorbable suture. We inserted a chest tube in one patient who came with an additional injury in the artery, further treated with left thoracotomy. Left and right thoracotomy received rectification subsequently. Eleven right chambers, six left ventricles, four right atriums and one atrium were injured. Two patients received injuries due to gunshots. The left upper lobe received common injuries. We exercised CPB on (18) patients to mend

the heart injuries. We employed necessary techniques to release the tamponade and then gave cardiac massage to the patients. The hemodynamics displayed considerable improvements in limited time. We also recorded the exercise of auxiliary median sternotomy where it was mandatory and then administered CPB. The wound due to compression split to the secondary artery. Though this study file total (6) complications during the observation and research project. One of the patients died owing to supplementary abdominal injury instead of cardiac injury.

Table: Injured Cardiac Chamber and Pulmonary Lobe Stratification (22)

Location		Number	Percentage
Injured Cardiac Chamber	Right ventricle	11	50.00
	left ventricle	6	27.27
	Right atrium	4	18.18
	Left atrium	1	4.55
Injured Pulmonary Lobe	Left upper lobe	13	59.09
	Left lower lobe	4	18.18
	Right upper lobe	3	13.64
	Right lower lobe	2	9.09

DISCUSSION:

Cardiac injuries are always challenging for the subjects and specialists during trauma surgery [3]. So, surgery is preferable for the patients who report with injuries to the heart and lungs [7]. Ultrasonography is an optimal choice during the phase of recovery from blockage, hem peritoneum and hem thorax [8]. Ultrasonography and echocardiography are the best choices to assess heart wounds [9]. Echocardiography is mandatory because it gives a complete picture of the heart structure and leads to surgical procedures [10]. Though it has some limitations [3]. Some patients show complete stable situation, for those, diagnosis can be overlooked [9]. So, to avoid such complications, subjects must acquire the necessary knowledge about cardiac injuries and survival. Good management of the situation can be helpful for survival [11]. Cardiac tamponades have its own pros and cons, at the initial level it restricts the release of blood but later in can stop the cardiac functioning [5, 12, 13]. The common exercise of anaesthesia can obstruct these reflexes and cardiac arrest may occur in the near future [14]. So, we covered all the subject prior to intubation. To gain access to the heart and other major vessels we used median sternotomy [15]. Median sternotomy is the best choice despite where multiple injuries are expected. Because it helps to uplift the heart for maintenance of posterior walls' wounds. So, this is the best technique to encounter the injuries in mediastinal vessels [12]. As oppose to this practice, some scholars prefer routine thoracotomy [7]. Because for the access to the left and right ventricles,

left thoracotomy is very suitable. Though the technique of thoracotomy is less advantageous for right atrium as well as for inferior or superior caval vein [15]. Similarly, Chinese surgeons usually prefer the technique of thoracotomy for the patients who report with injuries to the walls of their hearts [7]. However, most of the injuries are manageable without using CPB. Although many cases have reported that utilization of CPB can be blessing in terms of lifesaving as it can revert hypothermia, shock and acidosis. Additionally, it creates more time for taking additional measures to mend the cardiac wall more accurately [10, 16]. Revascularization or ligation is the best treatment for the maintenance of the coronary artery. Air bubbles are very common in coronary vessels [19]. So, it is important to examine coronary vessels before surgery so that fatalities could be avoided. We observed that the right ventricle which mainly contains an anterior area of the heart is a highly vulnerable and affected chamber. Tube thoracostomy is very useful when the vascular system shows low pressure and concentration increases in the tissues of the lungs [20]. In the last, we recommend that the conducting members should not take out the penetrating instrument till the cardiac evaluation prior to the operation and to the readiness of surgeon's specialist team is ready to execute CPB in case of requirement. Rather team must try to stabilize this instrument [10].

CONCLUSION:

Our involvement and familiarity with the combined cases of lungs and cardiac wounds demonstrated that

such case must be treated with immediate surgeries on priority bases. It also affirms that, presently, this the only possible way to bring the patients and affected subjects back to life. So, the surgical approach can be a lifesaving factor for the patients. Additionally, we suggest that professionals and specialists must consider the cardiac wounds amongst the patients who report with chest injuries or the wounds in upper abdominal areas.

REFERENCES:

1. Yillik L, Ergunes K, Yetkin U, Yasa H, Gurbuz A. Current evaluation of penetrating cardiac injuries. *T Klin J Cardiovascular Surgery* 2003; 4:121-125.
2. Degiannis E, Bowley DM, Westby S. Technical tutorial, notes and tips. *Ann R Coll Surg Eng* 2005; 87:6163.
3. Dauphine C, Mckay C, De Virgilio C, O Mari B. Selective use of cardiopulmonary bypass in trauma patients. *Am Surg* 2005; 71:46-50.
4. Narayan P, Caputo M, Roidl M, Casula R. The use of off-pump surgery for management of penetrating coronary artery injury. *Eur J Cardio-Thorac Surg* 2002; 21:361-362.
5. Vasquez JC, Baciewicz FA. Late-onset angina after penetrating cardiac injury adjacent to a coronary artery. *J Trauma* 2006; 60:1344-1346.
6. Demetriades D. Cardiac wounds. *Ann Surg* 1986; 203:315-317.
7. Velmahos GC, Butt MU. Cardiac and pulmonary injury. *Eur J Trauma Emerg Surg* 2008; 4:327-337.
8. Mardan MAA, Alshaeb A, Haddad OCM, Nafea AMS. *Gomal J Med Sci* 2008; 6:120-123.
9. Gao JM, Gao YH, Wei GB, Liu GL, Tian XY, Hu P, et al. Penetrating cardiac wounds: Principles for surgical management. *World J Surg* 2004; 28:1025-1029.
10. Menaker J, Cushman J, Vermillion JM, Rosenthal RE, Scalea TM. Ultrasound-diagnosed cardiac tampon after blunt abdominal trauma-treated with emergency thoracotomy. *J Emerg Med* 2007; 32:99-103.
11. Chang WY, Hsu JY, Chang YP, Chao CS, Chang KJ. The successful management of a penetrating cardiac injury in a regional hospital: A Case Report. *J Emerg Crit Care Med* 2008; 19:160-165.
12. Topcuoglu MS, Poyrazoglu HH, Yaliniz H. An unusual case of right lung and right atria-inferocaval injury caused by stabbing. *Thorac Cardiovascular Surg* 2009; 57:243-249.
13. Kang N, Hsee L, Rizoli S, Alison P. Penetrating cardiac injury: Overcoming the limits set by nature. *Injury* 2009; 40:919-927.
14. Degiannis E, Loogna P, Doll D, Bonanno F, Bowley DM, Smith MD. Penetrating cardiac injuries: Recent experience in South Africa. *World J Surg* 2006; 30:1258-1264.
15. Tokcan A, Kisacikoglu B, Salih OK, Ulus T, Tansal S, Oskay MK. Penetrating cardiac injuries: an analysis of 66 cases. *J Islamic Academy Sci* 1990; 3:62-65.
16. Kurimoto Y, Kano H, Yama N, Nara S, Hase M, Asai Y. Out of hospital cardiopulmonary arrest due to penetrating cardiac injury treated by percutaneous cardiopulmonary support in the emergency room: A Case Report *Surg Today* 2007;37:240-242.
17. Aksoyek A, Tutun U, Babaroglu S, Parlar AI, Ulus AT, Katircioglu SF. Penetrating cardiac injuries. *Ulus Travma Acil Cerrahi Derg* 2007; 13:135-141.
18. Asensio JA, Soto SN, Forno W, Roldan G, Petrone P, Gambaro E, et al. Penetrating cardiac injuries: A complex challenge. *Surg Today* 2001; 31:1041-1053.
19. Asensio JA, Soto SN, Forno W, Roldan G, Petrone P, Salim A, et al. Penetrating cardiac injuries: A complex challenge. *Injury* 2001; 32:533-543.
20. Asensio JA, Petrone P, Karsidag T, Ramos-Kelly R, Demiray S, Roldan G, et al. Penetrating cardiac injuries. Complex injuries and difficult challenges. *Ulus Travma Derg* 2003; 9:1-16.